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Open-access simulation dataset of the floating wind turbine DeepCwind OC4 in wind and waves

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Abstract. This paper focuses on the impact of various wind and wave conditions on the motion, tower base forces/moments and mooring line tension of a reference Floating Offshore Wind Turbine (FOWT) platform. The simulations are performed using OpenFAST to assess a total of 576 operational and 576 damaged scenarios. Selected results are presented to assess the impact of three different hydrodynamic modelling: i) Linear Potential Flow (LPF) ii) LPF combined with Morison drag (hybrid) and iii) hybrid approach with the inclusion of Quadratic Transfer Function (QTF). The importance of including the Morison drag term is demonstrated by assessing the platform's transient motion and the contribution of the heave disk to the heave motion. The impact of mean-drift from the difference-frequency second-order wave forces is evaluated by analysing the surge motion of the platform, comparing it with the LPF-only model. Power Spectral Density (PSD) of the tower base moment reveals several peaks in the frequency range corresponding to the contribution of the sum-frequency QTF. The impact of including QTF is more apparent for shorter wave periods. The loss of one mooring line has been found to increase the fairlead tension amplitude and induces higher load in the low-frequency region, visible on the PSD of the fairlead tension. Lastly, different wind directions are analysed to assess the impact of aerodynamic load to the mooring system, keeping the same wave direction. The wind-wave misalignment induces higher peak tensions in the lower frequency region, close to its surge natural frequency. The datasets containing a total of 1152 simulation cases results are made publicly available.

1. Introduction

Capacity factor is a ratio of the average energy produced within a certain time period divided by its maximum possible output (i.e., full capacity) that could have been generated. Therefore, it is an important parameter to measure the efficiency of a wind turbine. Recent data from 2024 suggests that offshore wind turbines in European Union countries generate an annual average of a 35% capacity factor [1]. Furthermore, the Hywind Scotland Floating Offshore Wind Turbines (FOWTs) can generate up to 57% of capacity factor [2]. As of 2023, offshore wind makes up 75.2 GW of total capacity globally where 14% of them were installed during that year [3]. Out of this number, around 270 MW installed capacity comes from the floating offshore wind turbines [4]. Floating technology is a recent emerging development that will allow wind turbines to be installed

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in a water depth deeper than 60.0 m where 80% of the offshore wind potential lies [5]. Thus, FOWT can unlock the untapped potential of harnessing electricity in deeper waters with greater capacity factor than nearshore or onshore. To this end, several collective efforts have been made in the past decades to investigate the different types of floaters and understand the physical aspects involved in modelling the dynamics of a floating wind turbine system [6 - 11]. Due to its complexity, numerical modelling of an FOWT system generally requires coupling between several modules that simulate different aspects: aerodynamics, hydrodynamics, structural dynamics, turbine control system, mooring dynamics. There exists several numerical tools that can be used to perform the global response time-domain analysis of an FOWT system such as OpenFAST, OrcaFlex, OPASS, Bladed, HAWC2, aNySIM, PHATAS, 3DFloat, DeepLines Wind, SAMCEF, Sesam, UTWInd [12]. The output of these tools may include hundreds of different channels e.g. 6 Degrees of Freedom (6-DOF) platform's motions, mooring line tension, sum of forces at a reference point, tower base/top forces and moments, power generated, thrust forces and moments. The aforementioned software are considered as mid-fidelity models which require a fine-tuning of coefficients obtained from the experiment or computational fluid dynamics (CFD) [13].

The experimental validation study and the use of higher-fidelity Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) and Finite Element Method (FEM) are performed at the detailed design phase, after the optimisation study is done using the lower to mid fidelity models [14]. At this phase, detailed structural checks for the platform are necessary to conduct. However, the aforementioned global response analysis software generally considers the platform as a rigid body [15]. Thus, it neglects the stress distribution in the substructure. The lack of accurate representation of the distributed hydrodynamic pressure loads poses a challenge when determining the fatigue life of the critical regions in the platform [16]. One of the methods that can be utilized to tackle this issue is called pressure mapping[16-18]. This approach uses the results of the global response time-domain analysis and the Boundary Element Method (BEM) frequency-domain hydrodynamic analysis. The results of these analyses are then mapped into a quasi-static Finite Element (FE) model. Thus, the development of such a numerical tool requires the global response analysis results. Other than the physics-based numerical tools, the use of neural network with more than two hidden layers, Deep Learning (DL) techniques to model FOWT systems have been gaining traction in the recent years [19-22]. Due to its computational efficiency, this approach is commonly used to create a digital twin model of a particular FOWT system. However, the development of such a model requires different datasets for training, testing and validation. These datasets can come from the aforementioned mid-fidelity software. The aim of the study conducted in this paper is to aid the development of different numerical tools, whether to build shell element for pressure mapping, DL, black-box models or any tools related to the modelling of FOWT system. This is done by providing benchmark simulation datasets of global response time-domain analysis.

2. Methodology

2.1 OpenFAST

An open-source Aero-Servo-Hydro-Elastic (AHSE) software called OpenFAST v3.5.3 [23] is used to perform the numerical simulations conducted in this paper. The flowchart consisting of the OpenFAST modules used in this study is shown in **Figure 1**. Note that WAMIT [24] frequency-domain outputs, consisting of hydrodynamic coefficients (i.e. added mass and damping), wave first order excitation force and total second-order wave forces (sum- and difference-frequency) are used by the HydroDyn module to calculate the hydrodynamic force in the time-domain. In

HydroDyn, the hydrodynamic force can be calculated by combining the Linear Potential Flow (LPF) theory and the Morison equation [25]. The LPF theory account for the wave excitation force (diffraction and Froude-Krylov) and the radiation force. Using the frequency-domain coefficients, the Impulse Response Function (IRF) and infinite added mass are calculated to account for the memory effect in the Cummins equation [26, 27]. Viscous effect can be modelled by including the drag term of the Morison equation [25]. As for the wind input, TurbSim [28] is used to generate the Full-Field (FF) turbulent wind. This is used by the InflowWind module to calculate the undisturbed wind velocities at various points around the wind turbine [29]. The output of InflowWind is used by the AeroDyn [30] module to calculate the aerodynamic load acting on the

Figure 1. OpenFAST modules that were used to perform the simulations in this study, adapted from [35]

turbine blades and the tower. The lumped-mass based mooring line module called MoorDyn [31] is used to simulate the dynamic behaviour of the mooring lines.

2.2 Numerical model setup and verification

Figure 2 shows the frontal view (YZ plane) of the reference FOWT system used in this study. The detailed specification and dimension can be found in the documentation for the DeepCwind OC4 semi-submersible definition [31]. The FOWT platform is paired with the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) 5 MW reference turbine where its specification is described in [32]. The numerical model for this reference turbine and platform is available on OpenFAST GitHub platform. This model is used as a basis for the simulations conducted in this paper. To ensure that the model is working correctly, selected load cases are simulated and compared against the numerical benchmark results published in [7].

Figure 2. XZ plan view of the reference FOWT system (7).

Numerical simulations of decay tests for the moored system are performed for three different DOFs: surge, heave, pitch. The results from the decay tests simulations are compared with the results of DeepLines and OrcaFlex in [34]. **Table 1** shows the natural frequencies and periods in surge, heave and pitch, obtained from the simulated decay tests. The results are nearly identical to the ones produced by DeepLines and OrcaFlex with the biggest discrepancy found in the surge motion with an error of less than 2%. In addition to the decay tests, the Load Case (LC) 3.1 from [7] that combines wind and wave inputs are used to verify the model in this study. The uniform and steady wind velocity is set at 8.0 m/s. Regular wave height is set at 6.0 m with the wave period of 10.0 s. Both wind and wave are aligned and perpendicular to the nacelle, propagating in positive x-axis. As shown in **Figure 3** left, the 3-DOF responses are showing good agreement where the peaks and troughs are matching the reference results of DeepLines and OrcaFlex. Similar trend can also be found in the fairlead tensions, shown in **Figure 3** right, with a slight underprediction of the minimum tension in fairlead 2 from this study.

Table 1. Natural frequencies and periods compared against the simulated decay tests results in [7]

Software [-]	Surge	Heave	Pitch
	Frequency - Period	Frequency - Period	Frequency - Period
OpenFAST v3.5.3 - This study	0.0089 Hz - 111.12 s	0.0566 Hz - 17.653 s	0.0400 Hz - 25.0 s
OrcaFlex	0.0092 Hz - 109.09 s	0.0567 Hz - 17.647 s	0.0400 Hz - 25.0 s
DeepLines WT	0.0092 Hz - 109.09 s	0.0567 Hz - 17.647 s	0.0400 Hz - 25.0 s

2.3 Simulation cases

A total of 1152 individual simulation cases were generated and the results were uploaded as open-access datasets to the Zenodo platform. The download link is provided in [34]. Shown in **Table 2** are the simulation matrix for the regular wave cases. All the combinations of the simulation variables (i.e., 2 scenario, 4 wave height, 4 wave period, 2 wind speed, 3 wind direction, 2 wind field) are simulated, resulting in a total of 384 unique simulation cases. The irregular wave cases have a total of 768 simulations with the combinations shown in **Table 3**.

Figure 3. Platform’s motions (left) and mooring fairlead tensions (right) results compared against LC 3.1.

Table 2. Simulation matrix for the regular waves cases.

Scenario [-]	Wave height [m]	Wave period [s]	Wind speed [m/s]	Wind direction [deg]	Wind field [-]
Operational	3.0	8.0	8.0	0.0	Steady
Fairlead loss	6.0	10.0	13.0	30.0	Turbulent
	9.0	12.0		45.0	
	12.0	20.0			

Table 3. Simulation matrix for the irregular waves cases.

Scenario [-]	Significant wave height [m]	Wave peak period [s]	Wind speed [m/s]	Wind direction [deg]	Wind field [-]
Operational	1.5	8.0	8.0	0.0	Steady
Fairlead loss	3.0	10.0	11.0	30.0	Turbulent
	4.5	12.0		45.0	
	6.0	20.0		20.0	

3. Results and discussions

3.1 Influence of hydrodynamic models

Three hydrodynamic models are compared to assess their influence on the floater’s responses:

- Linear Potential Flow (LPF) only.
- LPF with the inclusion of Morison drag (hybrid).
- LPF with the inclusion of Morison drag and second-order wave forces via Quadratic Transfer Function (QTF).

Table 4. Simulation matrix for the comparison of the hydrodynamic models

Scenario [-]	Significant wave height [m]	Wave peak period [s]	Wind speed [m/s]	Wind direction [deg]	Wind field [-]
Operational	6.0	8.0, 10.0, 12.0, 20.0	11.0	0	Steady

The input variables used in the simulations for this comparison are listed in **Table 4**. Note that the wave kinematics are only calculated up to the mean water level as no kinematic stretching is implemented in the aforementioned hydrodynamic models. During the transient part of the simulation, the inclusion of Morison drag dampened the surge response sooner compared to the LPF-only model, as shown in **Figure 4**. This is most pronounced for the wave peak period of 8.0 seconds where it takes more than 400 s for the surge response of LPF-only model to converge with the hybrid approach without QTF. In the case of the longest waves (20.0 s peak period), the influence of Morison drag to the surge motion is not apparent. On the other hand, influence of the mean-drift from the difference-frequency QTF can be seen in the shorter waves, especially for the peak period of 8.0 s. In this case, the platform is displaced further in the surge direction compared to the LPF-only and hybrid approach. **Figure 5** shows the heave response during the transient zone. This shows that the omission of the Morison axial drag causes the heave motion to be exaggerated throughout the simulation time, not only in the transient zone. This is because of the wave period that is close to the heave natural period of 17.65 s which induces resonance.

Figure 4. Time series of the surge motion comparing different hydrodynamic models

Figure 5. Time series of the heave motion comparing different hydrodynamic models

Figure 6 and **7** show the Power Spectral Density (PSD) of the surge motion and heave, respectively, considering all simulation data (1 hour). In **Figure 6**, it can be seen that including second-order wave forces induces the peaks in the lower frequencies region. An exception appears for the wave peak period of 12.0 s where the (lower frequencies) peak is higher for the LPF only model compared to the model that includes Morison and QTF. This is because the omission of Morison drag induces large initial surge motion during the transient part of the simulation. Note that these peaks are close to the natural frequency of the surge motion which is at 0.00899 Hz. Observing the PSD of the heave motion, it can be seen from the **Figure 7** that the heave resonance peak at 0.056 Hz is consistent across all wave peak periods when Morison (axial) drag is not modelled. Therefore, highlighting the importance of a heave disk to dampen the heave response. Furthermore, the influence of QTF to the heave motion is apparent across shorter wave peak periods (i.e., 8.0 s and 10.0 s), which can be seen from the peaks in the lower frequencies region (i.e., lower than the wave peak frequency). Lastly, as shown in **Figure 8**, modelling the QTF induces tower base pitch moment in both lower and higher frequency regions. This is due to the difference-frequency and sum-frequency components of the QTF, respectively.

Figure 6. PSD of the surge motion comparing different hydrodynamic models

Figure 7. PSD of the heave motion comparing different hydrodynamic models

Figure 8. PSD of the tower base pitch moment comparing different hydrodynamic models

3.2 Damaged scenario – loss of fairlead 2

This analysis compares the damaged and operational scenarios for the same wind and wave conditions. The damaged condition is simulated by removing fairlead 2 before starting the simulation. The input variables used in this comparison are summarized in **Table 5**. The platform’s responses in surge, heave and pitch are shown in **Figure 9**. It can be seen that the platform drifts for more than 800 m before it starts to oscillate around its new position where the remaining mooring lines are fully stretched. Note that the platform pitches more as the mooring

Table 5. Simulation matrix for the comparison of the damaged scenario

Scenario [-]	Significant wave height [m]	Wave peak period [s]	Wind speed [m/s]	Wind direction [deg]	Wind field [-]
Operational, damaged	6.0	8.0	13.0	0	Steady

lines pull the platform towards the positive x-axis. **Figure 10** shows the tension in fairlead 1 and 3. As expected, the damaged scenario results in higher tension in mooring lines 1 and 3 compared to the operational scenario. Furthermore, the loss of 1 mooring line induces low-frequency loads in the remaining mooring lines, in addition to the wave-induced load.

Figure 9. Platform's surge, heave and pitch responses comparing damaged and operational scenario

Figure 10. Fairlead 1 (top) and 3 (bottom) tension comparing damaged and operational scenario

3.3 Impact of wind-wave misalignment

Summarized in **Table 6** are the simulation inputs used for the comparison of the wind-wave misalignment. Three different wind directions are compared: 0, 30 and 45 degrees. **Figure 11** shows the comparison of tension PSD in fairlead 1, 2 and 3 for the different wind directions. Although the 0 deg (wind-wave aligned) results in the highest tension overall (at fairlead 2), the wind-wave misalignment induces higher load in the lower frequency region. As shown in **Figure 11**, the peaks in the frequency lower than 0.0089 Hz are higher for the 30 deg and 45 deg wind directions, especially for fairlead 1. This corresponds to the platform's surge natural frequency. Furthermore, tower base roll moment is induced for the 30 deg and 45 deg wind directions, with a similar order of magnitude as the tower base pitch moment, shown in **Figure 12**.

Table 6. Simulation matrix for the comparison of the wind-wave misalignment

Scenario [-]	Significant wave height [m]	Wave peak period [s]	Wind speed [m/s]	Wind direction [deg]	Wind field [-]
Operational	6.0	8.0	13.0	0, 30, 45	Steady

Figure 11. PSD of fairlead tensions comparing different wind directions

Figure 12. Tower base roll (top) and pitch (bottom) moments comparing different wind directions

4. Conclusions

This study highlights the impacts of different numerical modelling considerations: hydrodynamic models, mooring line damaged scenario and wind-wave misalignment. A total of 1152 simulation cases have been generated as open-access datasets [34]. From a selection of the simulation cases, the following conclusions are drawn:

- Including Morison drag dampened the motion quicker in the transient zone, especially for shorter wave periods.
- Including Morison axial drag in the heave disk dampened the heave response of the platform. This becomes increasingly important when the wave period is close to the heave natural period of 17.65 s.
- Mean-drift as the results of difference-frequency second-order wave forces is substantially more apparent for shorter wave periods below 12.0 s.
- The impact of difference- and sum-frequency QTF are apparent on the tower base moment. Indicating the importance of QTF in tower base moment calculation.
- Loss of one mooring line results in higher loads not only in the wave frequency region but also in the low-frequency region, lower than the surge natural frequency.
- Simulating wind-wave misalignment induces tower base moment in both pitch and roll axes. Additionally, it induces low-frequency load in the fairlead tensions.

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Data availability

The open-access simulation datasets can be downloaded from the Zenodo platform: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14223737>

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